

European Open Science Cloud

Jisc Briefing Paper

Matthew Dovey & Helen Clare, February 2025 [DOI 10.5281/zenodo.15384582]

Brief History

The European Open Science Cloud (EOSC) is an EC initiative started in 2015 with the ambition “to provide European researchers, innovators, companies and citizens with a federated and open multi-disciplinary environment where they can publish, find and reuse data, tools and services for research, innovation and educational purposes.” As well as being a highly ambitious undertaking, its genesis was an amalgamation of different agendas from different parts of the commission:

- The European Parliament saw this as a key stage in their **Cloud Initiative** – which would ultimately provide a European Cloud infrastructure with research as the initial implementation which would be then extended first for use by governments, and then SMEs.
- DG-RTD saw this as addressing the recommendations of their then recent “**Science 2.0**” consultation (one of which was that researchers didn’t like the term “Science 2.0”, preferring “Open Science”) in terms of making research data more accessible and re-usable.
- DG-CNECT saw this as a means of rationalizing their then current investments in e-infrastructure services (**GÉANT** for Network, **EGI** and **PRACE** for Compute, **EUDAT** for Data, **RDA** for Standards, etc.)

As a result, there have been different, sometimes competing, views of what EOSC is – for example, whether its focus should be on data or services, with the first High Level Expert Group concentrating on FAIR data, and the second on cloud services.

Since 2015, the EOSC has been developed through a number of EC funded projects (under FP7, Horizon 2020 and Horizon Europe), two High Level Expert Groups, an EOSC Board, and more recently the formation of the EOSC Association in 2021 and an open procurement leading to the launch of the EOSC-EU node in autumn 2024.

Current Status

Governance

The EOSC Tripartite collaboration is a concept of strategic coordination between:

- the EU represented by the European Commission. This involves **Directorate-General for Research and Innovation** (DG-RTD) and the **Directorate-General for Communications Networks, Content and Technology** (DG-CNECT).
- the participating countries represented in the **EOSC Steering Board** (EOSC-SB), an expert group of the European Commission composed of the 27 EU countries and countries associated to the specific programme implementing Horizon Europe and co-chaired by a representative of the European Commission and a representative of the other members of the group.
- the research community represented by the **EOSC Association** to resource and support the implementation of the EOSC ecosystem in Europe. EOSC AISBL was set up in July 2020 as an

international non-profit organisation under Belgian law with the aim to provide a single voice for advocacy and representation for the broader EOSC stakeholder community.

Plans are currently in progress for post-2027 governance and funding and discussion is ongoing with the EC, with different approaches proposed for the high-level tasks that have been defined for EOSC below:

- Deploying and operating the EOSC EU node (Core, Exchange, FAIR data federation)
- Maintaining and updating the EOSC EU node and expanding the federation
- Enabling a ‘web of FAIR data and services’
- Develop, prototype and test new elements supporting the evolution of EOSC Core, Exchange and federation
- Enabling open science policies and the uptake of open science practices

Strategy

The direction of EOSC is outlined in its **Strategic Research and Innovation Agenda (SRIA)**, which includes a set of guiding principles, implementation challenges, boundary conditions and expected impacts, followed by the Multi-Annual Roadmap (MAR).

SRIA 2.0 has been postponed due to the imminent developments around governance and the next framework programme. The latest version of the SRIA (v1.3) was released in December 2024. It included a Multi-Annual Roadmap (MAR) for 2026-27 which introduced four new ‘strategic pillars’:

- Sustaining and enhancing the EOSC Federation
- Contributing to the web of FAIR data and the uptake of AI
- Ensuring research security and sovereignty
- Linking with other Common European Data Spaces and beyond

The recent **EOSC Winter School** convened in January 2025 provided the opportunity for task forces, expert groups and projects to reframe activities around these pillars.

A **macro-roadmap for the implementation of EOSC** has been developed, which is an interactive catalogue of the results of EU projects developing EOSC, the deliverables of the EOSC-A Task Forces, and selected in-kind contributions of the EOSC-A membership. These three inputs are tracked over time and categorized according to selected high-level objectives and the respective Action Areas of the EOSC Partnership’s Strategic Research & Innovation Agenda.

Building the EOSC Federation - EOSC Nodes

According to the **EOSC Association Board position paper on the EOSC Federation and the role of EOSC nodes**, EOSC “is envisioned as a federation of distributed systems, combined into a system of systems, consisting of multiple ‘EOSC Nodes’ that are interconnected and can collaborate to share and manage information and resources within and across thematic and geographical research communities”. The EOSC Association web site outlines key activities around **building the EOSC Federation**.

Exactly how nodes are defined and how the structure will work is still under discussion, but it will be underpinned by existing NRENs and Research Infrastructures (RIs). Jisc contributed to the development of the **GÉANT position paper on behalf of NRENs** which has been influential in steering the thinking of the EOSC Association.

A key output for the EOSC Association in 2024 is a **EOSC Federation Handbook** which “will comprehensively address the purpose, structure, governance, architecture and operations of the EOSC Federation”. In 2024 a smaller ‘Tripartite Group’ was formed of selected members to provide input into the development of the EOSC Federation Handbook. A draft of the first three chapters was released for consultation at the end of 2024. Following feedback from consultation and the Tripartite Group a first full version is due to be released in March 2025 and the handbook will be revised regularly as the federation builds.

The **EOSC-EU Node** was launched in September 2024, taking over running the core services created as part of the flagship **EOSC Future project**. The EOSC EU node is funded by a procurement rather than project funding to ensure more stability and consistency in future. Further nodes will follow to build the federation.

In February **thirteen candidate nodes were announced** after a selection process, representing potential European, national and thematic Nodes distributed across the continent. A kick-off workshop will take place in March 2025 which was announced as 'signalling the opening act in EOSC's build-up phase'.

European Data Spaces

The **European Cloud Initiative** within which the EOSC was first formed, has been superseded by the **European Data Strategy** which proposes **Common Data Spaces** across fourteen domains: Agriculture; Cultural Heritage; Energy; Finance; Green deal; Smart cities and communities; Health; Language; Manufacturing; Media; Mobility; Public administration; Research and Innovation; Skills; Tourism. EOSC is considered to be the key enabler of the Research and Innovation Data Space, whereas development of the other Data Spaces fall within the Digital Europe programme.

The EOSC-A Board has regular meetings with representatives of the **Data Spaces Support Centre** (DSSC) to continue discussion initiated last year on how to strengthen the collaboration between the two initiatives. A draft joint roadmap is currently under preparation to identify actions to enable technical interoperability, strengthen strategic alignment, enhance cross-fertilisation of the two initiatives at thematic level and maximise community engagement.

EOSC Task Forces and Expert Groups

Following the end of the latest group of Task Forces in late 2023 the EOSC Association reviewed activities and defined different mechanisms for engagement with research community members, beyond EOSC projects:

- **Task Forces from Advisory Groups:** groups of experts formed through an open call chaired by two elected experts from EOSC-A member organisations. Limited duration with own workplan and deliverables. Four Task Forces were launched in 2024:
 - Technical and Semantic Interoperability of the EOSC Federation
 - Long-term Digital Research Objects Retention
 - FAIR metrics and Digital Objects
 - Health Data (new Task Force)
- **Opportunity Area Expert Groups (OAEG)** - groups of experts from EOSC projects, plus additional experts with relevant expertise. The seven Opportunity Areas are:
 - OA1: PIDs
 - OA2: Metadata, Ontologies & Interoperability
 - OA3: FAIR Assessment & Alignment
 - OA4: User & Resource Environments
 - OA5: Skills, Training, Rewards, Recognition & Upskilling
 - OA6: Open Scholarly Communication
 - OA7: Research software

Opportunities and Risks

Brexit

Brexit and the delays to Horizon Europe association have inevitably taken their toll on the UK's role and influence within EOSC. The UK was one of the thought-leaders during the formative stages of EOSC, however since the referendum, the UK's role and influence has declined both in terms of influence and engagement: UK participation in the later flagship projects, the EOSC Association and the taskforces has been low.

Whilst Association to Horizon Europe was a major step forward, issues still remained. In the current **Multi-annual Financial Framework** (MFF), the EC have separated more operational activities into a separate programme – **Digital Europe** – leaving Horizon Europe focused (in the main) on research and innovation. Digital Europe includes funding for Cybersecurity, **EuroHPC**, Quantum Networking, and the Common Data Spaces. Since EOSC is the only Data Space outside the Digital Europe programme it seems likely that this might be subsumed into successors to Digital Europe. There are similar concerns with other operational activities currently funded under Horizon Europe such as GÉANT. Whilst Association to Digital Europe is an option, this is typically targeted at

countries already on the accession path to joining the EC, and even then associated countries are explicitly excluded from parts of the work-programme (e.g. Cybersecurity).

The current development of the EOSC Nodes has been taken forward via a procurement route rather than a Horizon Europe project. Procurement of activities that the EC regards as critical infrastructure have restrictions which can limit the participation of organisations not based in EC member states.

Thought Leadership

In many ways, the EOSC is comparable with various initiatives to provide coherent and comprehensive digital services to researcher over the last 30 years, such as the [Jisc Information Environment programme](#); the [DTI e-Science programme](#); the BEIS e-Infrastructure programme; and the UKRI e-Infrastructure and Digital Research Infrastructure programmes. Association to Horizon Europe re-opens the opportunity for the UK to retake a leading role. The move from the EOSC Portal to EOSC Nodes marks a growing realisation that such initiatives are best not considered as a monolithic construct but more as a change process to encourage collaboration, re-use and interoperability which is a key message of the [Federation Journey report on UK digital infrastructure](#). The EOSC community is very likely to be receptive to the ideas of that report, and this would provide a foundation for re-establishing our credentials in this space.

Collaboration and Standards

It is important for UK Research and Innovation, that researchers can collaborate with their peers in the international research community, sharing and benefiting from research results, research data, research methodology, research tools etc. It is important that the UK Digital Research Infrastructure can fully interoperate with international infrastructures – not just at the technical level, but also semantically, organisationally and legally interoperable. It is key that the UK must engage with EOSC as

- The UK will need to implement EOSC interoperability standards in order for UK researchers to collaborate with not only researchers within the EC but, given that EOSC is also influencing the development of a “Global Open Science Cloud”, with international researchers in general;
- The UK will need to influence the EOSC interoperability standards to ensure that these meet the UK’s use cases and requirements.

Areas of particular interest, where the UK has previously been a world leader, include Access and Identity Management and Persistent Identifiers.

Financial

The financial and sustainability model of the EOSC is still a work in progress. Formally, EOSC is a jointly funded venture between the EC and the Member States. At present, the Member State contribution has been a contribution in kind, typically activities the Member State would have done anyway. However, the EC is increasingly expecting more directed contributions, which is likely to cause some frictions between the Member States and the EC. This has already surfaced in disagreements between the EC and the Member States on the EOSC Steering Board as regards using a Joint Undertaking (a legal construct of the Treaty on the Functioning of the European Union) for future funding of EOSC. The commitments being asked of countries wishing to be part of the EOSC may cause particular political problems for the UK.

A related issue is how resources or services are compensated if they are accessed through the EOSC. National facilities are funded by their local government for use by local researchers. If EOSC allows these facilities to be used internationally, how are the additional costs and overheads covered? Various mechanisms have been proposed ranging from this being the countries contribution to EOSC to “cloud coins”. Depending on the final solution, this could offer benefits such as additional income streams to Universities for providing spare resources and compute to EOSC, but also carries risks such as a government cutting funding for a resource because it is “free” via EOSC (without realising that the “free” service is the one they have just cut funding for).